

CARDIOHEALTH AND EMOTIONS

COMPLETE HEART

The heart acts as a pump which receives venous blood in the right atrium from all tissues. The pulmonary trunk drives it towards the lungs via the pulmonary arteries. After gas exchange, blood rich in oxygen comes back to the heart (left atrium) via the pulmonary veins and from here it is delivered to all tissues. The main vessels coming to the right atrium are the upper and lower cava veins. They carry venous blood with low levels of oxygen. The main vessel arising from the heart (left ventricle) is aorta. Ventricles are the main contracting part of the heart. They act as a pump and for this reason have inlet valves (right and left atrioventricular valves) and outlet valves (pulmonary and aortic valves). The complete hearts supplied in this kit depict the external and internal anatomy of the heart and the main vessels.

1. Right ventricle. 2. Left ventricle. 3. Right atrium (auricle). 4. Left atrium (auricle). 5. Aorta. 6. Pulmonary trunk. 7. Cranial vena cava. 8. Brachiocephalic trunk. 9. Left subclavian artery.

HEART SAGITTAL SECTION

This section is very appropriate to display the inner anatomy of the right and left atrium and the ventricles. Apart from some detailed information of the vales, it is important to relate the thickness of the ventricle wall with its function. The left ventricle is thicker as it should send blood from here to all parts of the body.

1. Right ventricle. 2. Left ventricle. 3. Interventricular septum. 4. Left atrium (auricle). 5. Left atrioventricular valve (mitral). 6. Aortic valve. 7. Aorta. 8. Pulmonary trunk.

TRANSVERSAL SECTION OF HEART

This section has been taken at the level of the valves. Right (tricuspid) and left (mitral) atrioventricular valves are located on the right and caudal part of the heart. Pulmonary valve is located on the left side (cranially to the left atrium) and aortic valve is easily identified in the middle of the heart.

1. Right atrium (auricle). 2. Right atrioventricular foramen. 3. Right atrioventricular valve (tricuspid). 4. Caudal cava vein. 5. Left atrium (auricle). 6. Left atrioventricular valve (mitral). 7. Aortic valve. 8. Pulmonary valve

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